

Challenges for Organizations in Dynamic Business Environment

Impact of Foreign Direct Investment in Indian Economy

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ABSTRACT

Foreign capital & technology can play a very important role in the socio-economic development of the nation. The opening up of the economy has led to rapid increase in foreign direct investment & foreign exchange reserves. So, attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) has become a key part of national development strategies for many countries. FDI refers to investment in a foreign country, where the investor retains the control over the investment. It typically takes the form of starting the subsidiary, acquiring the stake in an existing firm or starting the joint venture in the foreign country. Direct investment & management of the firms concerned normally go together. FDI is like a proprietary capital and is the only capital inflow that has been strongly associated with higher GDP growth since 1970. They see such investments as bolstering domestic capital, productivity, and employment, all of which are crucial to jump-starting economic growth. FDI benefits domestic industries as well as the Indian consumers by providing opportunities for technological up gradation, access to global managerial skills and practices, optimal utilization of resources, making industry competitive. When the exports earnings are insufficient to finance such vital imports, foreign capital could help reduce the foreign exchange gap. Moreover, FDI are governed by the long term considerations because these investments cannot be easily liquidated. Hence, factors like long term political stability, government policy; industrial and economic prospects etc influence the FDI decision. Direct investors have direct responsibility with the promotion and management of the enterprise. Besides, on the supply side, FDI is affected by the availability of investible funds from corporate profits or loans, which is in turn affected by domestic economic conditions. On the demand side, growing overseas markets lead TNCs to invest, while depressed markets inhibit them. The more interdependent host and home economies become, and the more widely a recession or upswing spreads, the greater are the corresponding movements in global FDI. Developing countries like India experience both strong capital accumulation and technology transfer through FDI. FDI's impact depends on many conditions, well-developed and implemented policies can help maximize its gains.

I would like to add India's FDI story too. India today is ranked among the most favoured destinations for Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), with the services sector at the top in attracting FDI in April-November 2006. India has also emerged as the most attractive FDI destination in Asia with an 18 percent rate of return on equity investments. Although India has substantially liberalized its foreign investment policy, the FDI inflows had been much below the targets. India had not been getting even one-tenth the size of FDI flow to China. Even the cumulative FDI flow to India between 1991 and 2007 was less the annual flow to china. In April-Nov. 2009-2010, FDI was 14,142(in \$mn). Bureaucratic problems, certain unfavorable government's attitudes, poor infrastructure, labour factors, high input costs etc are regarded as the major reasons. In this paper, we shall study in detail about the various impact of FDI.

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